

RESEARCH LETTER

A Growth Chart for KBG Syndrome

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In Low, Foreman, et al. (2025), we report a growth chart for females and males with *ANKRD11* and KBG syndrome (Figures 1 and 2). This growth chart was produced using 1417 data points from 101 individuals with KBG syndrome from the United Kingdom (DDD and GenROC cohorts (Firth et al. 2011; Low et al. 2024)), the Netherlands, Denmark, and Spain.

KBG syndrome is one of the most common monogenic neurodevelopmental disorders and is caused by pathogenic variants in *ANKRD11* (Low et al. 2016). There are ~800 known individuals worldwide based on published cases registrations with the patient organizations. KBG syndrome is a highly variable multisystem disorder which includes short stature, skeletal, dental, behavioral, neurological and cardiac abnormalities (Low et al. 2016; Ockeloen et al. 2015; de Boer et al. 2022; Martinez-Cayuelas et al. 2023) and has been well documented in multiple, predominantly pediatric cohorts in the literature.

Short stature has been described to date as a common but not universal feature of KBG Syndrome (He et al. 2024). In fact, many of the cases in the literature have normal stature, albeit with most in the lower half of the normal centile range. Questions have been raised about the role of growth hormone treatment in this condition (Reynaert et al. 2015) with a small number of cases treated (Aukema et al. 2025). Data are lacking regarding final adult height in treated cases. Microcephaly has been reported in some individuals, but many have normal head sizes. Weight is often normal, but feeding problems can affect

some individuals, with the most severe end of the spectrum requiring long-term PEG feeding; albeit, this is only seen in very small numbers. Cyclical vomiting is a rare but recognized feature as well.

The growth chart shows the downward shift of the 50th and 2nd centiles for *ANKRD11* for height, weight and OFC compared to the UK reference population. Children with KBG syndrome should be monitored with reference to these growth charts rather than relying on standard pediatric charts alone. Clinicians should bear in mind the impact of differences in growth due to country of origin and adjust for this accordingly—for example, a Dutch child would be expected to be taller than one from the United Kingdom and this would still be true for KBG syndrome.

We note that BMI rises in both males and females in adolescence. This is less likely to be specific to KBG syndrome and more likely to be reflective of a trend toward increasing obesity in adolescents in the wider population (we noted this for other genes too). Teenagers should be encouraged with healthy eating and exercise as per standard population recommendations. Many individuals with KBG syndrome have coexistent learning difficulties, neurodivergence, and sensory needs, and so strategies should be tailored to maximize understanding and success.

The debate regarding utility of growth hormone in KBG syndrome continues. These charts will provide an important clinical tool in determining the extent of their short stature in

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FIGURE 1 | Height, weight, BMI and OFC centile charts for females with KBG syndrome. The solid lines indicate the KBG-specific centiles. The dashed lines indicate the underlying population reference centiles (UK-90).

comparison to both the reference population and, importantly, in contrast to other children with KBG syndrome.

We collected final adult heights from 79 individuals with KBG syndrome aged 16 and over as part of the ‘Life beyond childhood—a study of KBG syndrome in adults’ study (Low, Walker, et al. 2025). The z-score distribution of these heights is shown in Figure 3 as compared to the z-score distribution for height for our *ANKRD11* growth chart dataset. This shows that the adults are relatively shorter than the children, which agrees with the suggestion in the limited literature of a possible post-pubertal growth deceleration. Data remain limited regarding whether growth hormone treatment definitively increases final adult height.

We would recommend that any child with KBG syndrome be assessed for short stature clinically and with reference to these charts. Growth velocity, bone age, and growth hormone deficiency investigations could be considered in those children who fulfill short stature criteria.

We consulted with the GenROC study participants regarding our growth charts and they were extremely positive that they would be very helpful clinically and to them as families.

Nicola, Charlie's mum, explains why participating in the study meant so much to her: “The GenROC study caught my eye when I connected with other families whose children also had KBG syndrome.”

During Charlie's first year, he struggled to gain weight, and it felt like we were under constant scrutiny from healthcare professionals. There were daily weigh-ins in the early weeks, followed by weekly weigh-ins. I was determined to continue breastfeeding, as I had successfully breastfed Charlie's older brother, even with his condition. But I felt enormous pressure to supplement with formula, even though I knew that would make feeding more difficult.

The healthcare teams seemed overly focused on numbers rather than seeing Charlie as an individual. I was sent to hospital with him on one occasion because of his lack of weight gain. He was labelled as having ‘failed to thrive’—a phrase that made me

FIGURE 2 | Height, weight, BMI and OFC centile charts for males with KBG syndrome. The solid lines indicate the KBG-specific centiles. The dashed lines indicate the underlying population reference centiles (UK-90).

feel like I was failing as a parent. And that label will remain on his medical records forever.

But the truth was, Charlie had not failed to thrive at all—he simply did not fit the generic growth charts. I chose to take part in this study to help ensure other families don't have to go through the same stressful experience we did.

Charlie was diagnosed with KBG syndrome just before his second birthday. Nicola wonders if, “being able to have shared data on growth may have been helpful before his diagnosis as medical professionals could have had access to a bank of data about growth patterns with different conditions. It may not have pointed to KBG but may have helped ease the pressure around feeding and growth.”

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, investigation, methodology: K.J.L., T.J.C. Formal analysis: T.J.C. Project administration, supervision, writing – original draft: K.J.L., T.J.C. Data curation, writing – review and editing: all authors.

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ANKRD11

FIGURE 3 | Distribution of final adult height z scores referenced to UK-90.

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Ethics Statement

The DDD study has UK Research Ethics Committee approval (10/H0305/83, granted by the Cambridge South REC, and GEN/284/12 granted by the Republic of Ireland REC). All participants gave informed consent, as required by the REC. All published data were de-identified. Specific ethical approval for the growth charts development was given via a DDD Complementary Analysis Proposal Approval (CAP#371). The GenROC study received East Midlands—Nottingham Research Ethics Committee (REC) approval on 15 December 2022 and Health Research Authority approval on 9 February 2023. The *ASXL3* Natural History Study, sponsored by Sheffield Children’s Hospital and The University of Sheffield (UK), received REC (23/SC/0151) and HRA approval on 2 June 2023. All participants enrolled in the study gave informed consent for anonymized data sharing to allow this collaboration.

Consent

Growth data are anonymized at an individual level and not linked to any identifiers. All GenROC and DDD participants consented to publication as part of study protocol.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

Variant and phenotype data for GenROC and DDD participants are available via DECIPHER. www.deciphergenomics.org.

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